

The Effect of Enhanced Telehealth on the Management of Type 2 Diabetes

Sarita Dhakal, DNP, RN, FNP --- Jill Berg, PhD, RN --- Joy R. Goebel, PhD, RN

Background

- ❖ In the United States, T2DM has become an overwhelming healthcare burden & is the seventh leading cause of death.
- ❖ Managing a chronic illness such as diabetes is challenging to patients & healthcare providers.
- ❖ According to CDC recommendations, patients with diabetes should see their health care provider regularly.
- ❖ A recent study found that missing health care appointments are directly associated with poor glycemic control.

Problem Statement

- ❖ The COVID 19 pandemic has resulted in the use of telehealth visits (TV) for clinic appointments.
- ❖ The necessity to rapidly integrate telehealth into clinical care has limited the ability to implement conceptually based, evidence-supported clinical practices.

Purpose

The Purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to assess whether an enhanced TV increases the % of kept appointments & glycemic control (as measured by the % of FBG levels in the range of 80-120 mg/dl) over a 3-month period at an outpatient endocrinology clinic..

Methods

Design: Quality Improvement (QI) project, telehealth intervention guided by the Chronic Care Model.

Participants: 15 patients with T2DM, 18 years and older, with an average HbA1c level $\geq 7.5\%$.
Setting: An outpatient endocrinology clinic in Orange County, CA.

Measures: Average weekly FBG levels, weekly appointment keeping, and Telehealth Usability Questionnaire (TUQ).

Framework

Standard Telehealth and Enhanced Telehealth		
Care Elements	Standard Telehealth	Enhanced Telehealth
Video Conferencing Platform	Zoom	Zoom
Provider	Nurse practitioner (author)	Nurse practitioner (author)
Care approach	Zoom at least every 3 months	Zoom + weekly phone calls
Diabetes Self-management		
Blood Glucose Monitoring	Discussed at least every 3 months via zoom	Discussed on weekly phone calls
Exercise	Discussed at least every 3 months via zoom	Discussed on weekly phone calls
Diet	Discussed at least every 3 months via zoom	Discussed on weekly phone calls
Medications	Discussed at least every 3 months via zoom	Discussed on weekly phone calls
Barriers to care	Discussed at least every 3 months via zoom	Discussed on weekly phone calls
Diabetes community resources	Discussed at least every 3 months	On the first Zoom meeting

Results

- ❖ Participants were mostly male, married & worked full time. Mean age was 57 years.
- ❖ At the onset of the project, all participants had an average FBG > 120 mg/dl.
- ❖ At the end of the project, 2/12 (16.6%) met the goal of an average FBG level within the range of 80-120 mg/dl. Average weekly FBG decreased from 251 mg/dl to 134 mg/dl at the end of 12 weeks.
- ❖ One hundred percent of participants kept all the appointments throughout the project although a complete data set was only available for 12 participants.
- ❖ Results from the TUQ were that the majority of participants were very satisfied with the TV.

Recommendations

- ❖ Enhanced TVs should be an option for all patients at any time.
- ❖ Important to maintain a secure and private enhanced TV system, so patients feel safe sharing their private information.
- ❖ The intervention may be expensive so alternative staff members may be able to place calls to patients.

Limitations

- ❖ Small # of participants and short duration of the intervention.
- ❖ The project took place during the second wave of the COVID-19 pandemic and participants were fearful of exposure.
- ❖ No opportunity to collect baseline data, so it was not possible to assess appointment keeping pre-pandemic.

Conclusion

Overall, enhanced TV interventions appear to be a promising tool in reducing FBG levels and improving health outcomes of T2DM patients.

References

